

**THE MOST IMPORTANT TASK OF APOLOGIZING IN UZBEK IS
PRAGMATIC AVV MEANINGFUL UNITS.**

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Abstract: In view of such interdependence of language and culture, we first limit the scope of this relational paradigm and develop an appropriate methodology (with adequate assumptions), and then proceed to examine the socialization of issues presented in different languages.

Key words: Customs, values, beliefs, traditions, knowledge, implicature, illocutionary force

One of the most important functions of apology is to achieve social harmony and what Lakoff (2003: 201) refers to metaphorically as 'greasing the social wheels'. He likes to see it in terms of "first and foremost a social movement." on politeness: "To apologize is to act politely ... paying attention to the facial needs of the addressee." Olstein says almost the same thing (1989:156): "In the decision to make a verbal apology, S (the speaker) is willing to humiliate himself to a certain extent...". one-off (that is, more self-deprecating).

Goffman (1971: 140) argues that an apology is a restoration of social balance, with the act of apologizing "participants feel that matters are closed and [social] balance is restored.

According to Cohen and Olstein (1993: 34), complicating the selection of appropriate strategies is the fact that apologies and other speech acts involve many social, cultural, situational, and personal factors.¹

According to Ruth Benedict (1949), culture is what binds (people) together. Culture is all the accepted and exemplary behavior of a particular people, such as behavior, taboos, folklore, clothing, music, etc.²

A very broad term, concept or word to consider, 'culture' undoubtedly has many different meanings and uses. Some people think of culture as practice and others as information. While practice is about using a particular learned code in a society or language, knowledge is about keeping it as static information and referring to it when needed. Because it is evident both in life and in language, where the message or metamessage is conveyed especially through the latter.

¹ Olshstein, Elite (1989). Apologies Across Languages. (Eds. S. Blum-Kulka, J. House, & G. Kasper), Cross-Cultural Pragmatics: Requests and Apologies. Norwood: Ablex Publishing, 155-173.

² Benedict, Ruth (1949). Patterns of Culture. Boston: Houghton Mifflin Company Publishing

So, it has a social point as a product of society and not individual. It has a growing or developing part because it can change by developing or diminishing through social interaction. Another aspect is that culture is shared through customs, values, beliefs, traditions or knowledge. Also, it is learned through conscious or unconscious behavior

Our limitation is in the direction of linguistic-cultural analysis of communication in English and Turkish, including the following issues:

- 1-Culture-based communicative behavior
- 2- Ways to apologize in English and Turkish
5. Teaching culture through language

After discussing the various traditional frameworks of speech acts in general, we now proceed to consider the speech act of apology in particular. The next section examines empirical research on apologetics, including cross-linguistic and cross-cultural studies.

Speech acts, a subfield of pragmatics, can be defined as actions performed with the help of words, that is, speech acts are important units of human communication. Here, a brief overview of the traditional speech act is given and the focus is on Austin's (1962) speech act theory, Searle's (1979) theory, and Grice's (1975) discourse influence. It is axiomatic that Austin's (1962) speech act theory, Searle's (1979) revised taxonomy of Austin's speech act classification system, and Gricean (1975) pragmatic theory of discourse implicature are classic contributions to the study of speech acts. philosophy and then pragmatics.

Apology is a speech act that has attracted the attention of various researchers from different disciplines. According to Holmes (1995), an apology is a polite speech act in which the person asking for forgiveness heals the offense by taking responsibility and, as a result, aims to restore social relations between the interlocutors. It was Austin who first introduced speech act theory (1962) and emphasized that language is used not only to say something, but also to do something. Years later, this theory was developed by Searle (1969), who defines speech acts as the basic unit of communication in which a speaker can express more than what he says. To express different relationships, the speaker uses speech acts that do not correspond to the context and to himself communicative intention—that is. illocutionary force. Each speech act corresponds to the attitude of the speaker. For example, to express a sentence, the speaker performs a belief, to express his anger, the speaker complains, or to express regret, he apologizes.

The success of a speech act as a part of communication is determined by the listener's recognition of the communicative intention of the speaker. According to Schmidt and Richards (1980), speech acts are all actions performed through speech, including attitudes, gestures, discourse, and context during communication.³

In addition, they define speech acts as actions performed through words that usually have more specific characteristics, such as a complaint, compliment, offer, promise, request, or apology.

According to Austin's (1962) theory, there are three types of meaning: locative act, indeterminate act, and perlocutionary act. A locative act is the act of a speaker saying something to someone. For example, if the speaker says⁴"this cake looks delicious". This phrase literally means "this cake looks delicious". The illocutionary act refers to the speaker's intention to fulfill the social function of what is said. In other words, when a speaker says something, he expresses a sentence with some task in mind. As a result, the speaker may express more than the literal meaning of the utterances. Therefore, "this cake looks delicious" can be interpreted as an indirect request that someone be offered a piece of cake. Disruptive action involves the effect the speaker wants to make on the listener. Thus, saying "that cake looks delicious" may cause the listener to take a piece of cake.

- 1) I admit I ate the hamster (Responsibility)
 - 2) It was wrong of me to eat the hamster / I shouldn't have eaten the hamster (wrongdoing/ regretting)
 - 3) Can you find it in your heart to forgive me for eating the hamster (Wish/request for forgiveness,
 - 4) I'll never eat a hamster again as long as I live (abjuration of bad behaviour)
 - 5) I'm sorry that I ate the hamster (apology)
 - 6) I'm sorry Mr Smith isn't available today (an expression of non responsible sympathy)
 - 7) Well I'm sorry! But you don't know what you are talking about (denial that an apology is in order (the examples are from Lakoff (2003: 202)
- These two synonyms are "apology" or have the same basic meaning "asking forgiveness". The analysis below is to show common and different grammatical patterns.

³ Lansdown, Richard (ed.) (2015) Byron's Letters and Journals :A new Selection. Oxford : Oxford University Press.

⁴ Lansdown, Richard (ed.) (2015) Byron's Letters and Journals :A new Selection. Oxford : Oxford University Press.

Bir xil grammatik ko'rsatkichlari	
I am sorry	I apologize
I am sorry + that clause	I apologize + that clause
I am sorry + if clause	I apologize + if clause
I am sorry + for + something	I apologize + for + something
I am sorry + but	I apologize + but
I am sorry + about	I apologize + about
I am sorry + and	I apologize + and
Various grammatical indicators	
I am sorry	I apologize
I am sorry + to say that	I apologize + for the fact that
I am sorry + to infinitive	I apologize + though
I am sorry + other (when)	I apologize + noun clause
	I apologize + to + someone
	I apologize + on behalf of
	I apologize + in advance
	Did/Should + I apologize

“Sorry” according to its semantic meaning, it is used in the context of admitting one's guilt or denying that one is guilty:

Oh, I'm sorry - I didn't see you there.

Tom, I'm so sorry about last night - it was all my fault.

I've said I'm sorry.

I'm sorry that I wasn't able to phone you yesterday.

I'm sorry I'm late. I'm genuinely sorry for what I said, I really am.

I'm sorry, I was only trying to be helpful.

I'm so sorry to keep you waiting.

b. "to say no" Used to show politeness when refusing or disagreeing with something:

I'm sorry

I'm sorry, but I think you've made a mistake.

I'm sorry, I can't agree. Exclamation

c. Adjective (pronoun): apology Used when apologizing for something:

"That's my foot you're stepping on." "Sorry!"

Sorry - I didn't catch what you said.

Sorry, could you say that again?

Sorry, this area is closed to the public.

Sorry, I can't let you in without identification.

Sorry, can I see your pass?

d. Adjective (pronoun): polite negation Used to show politeness when rejecting or disagreeing with something:

Sorry, you can't go in there. It is also used when politely asking someone to repeat something or when politely interrupting someone:

"He's late." "Sorry?" "I said he's late."

"Sorry, could you just say that last sentence again please?"

e. Adjective: sad It is used to express a feeling of sadness, sympathy or disappointment, especially because something unpleasant has happened or been done:

I'm just sorry about all the trouble I've caused her.

He'd really upset her and he didn't seem at all sorry. I'm sorry (that) you had such a difficult journey.

We were both sorry to hear you've been ill again.

I feel so sorry for their kids - it must be really hard for them.

f. Sorry is used to show that something that needs to be said causes sadness or disappointment:

I'm sorry to say that the project's funding has been cancelled. Most people who start the exercise class do,

I'm sorry to say, give up within the first two weeks.

"Sorry" also serves to express the following semantic content in communication:

a. Adjective: apologizing This means feeling bad because you have caused trouble or trouble for someone else:

I'm really sorry (that) I forgot about our appointment yesterday.

"Sorry", Also used as a polite way to apologize to someone for doing something that upsets you:

The train will be moving shortly – we are sorry for the inconvenience. Sorry is also used as a polite way to show your sympathy to someone because of a loss, problem, or trouble the person has had: We were sorry to learn about the death of your grandmother.

b. Adjective: polite refusal Used as a polite way of expressing refusal or disagreement.:

I'm sorry, but I think you've made a mistake in our check. Sorry, you can't go in there.

“Sorry” When the use of the word in different grammatical forms was analyzed, the following situations occurred:

So'zlar	Frequency in BNC (times)
<i>I am sorry-that clause</i>	21
<i>I am sorry to say that</i>	15
<i>I am sorry + to infinitive</i>	12
<i>I am sorry + if clause</i>	5
<i>I am sorry + for + something</i>	5
<i>I am sorry + for + someone</i>	3
<i>I am sorry + but</i>	2
<i>I am sorry + about</i>	1
<i>I am sorry + and</i>	1
<i>I am sorry + other</i>	-

References:

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4. Phoocharoensil, S. (2010). A Corpus-Based Study of English Synonyms. International Journal of Arts and Sciences, 3(10): 227 – 245